

The Study of Fuel Consumption for Idling Stop Systems in Different Traffic Conditions

Wen-Kung Tseng ✉

Graduate Institute of Vehicle Engineering,
National Changhua University of Education, Taiwan R. O. C.

Tsung-Jen Mai

Graduate Institute of Vehicle Engineering,
National Changhua University of Education, Taiwan R. O. C.

Article History:

Received: 07.02.2025 Revised: 10.03.2025 Accepted: 12.03.2025 Published: 13.03.2025

ABSTRACT:

Idling stop systems have been used to improve engine fuel consumption during vehicle stopping. The idling stop technology would turn off the engine when the vehicle is in a stationary condition (often in areas with heavy urban traffic). When the traffic begins moving the driver releases the brake pedal to start the engine to provide vehicle power and drive on the road. In urban traffic congested road conditions, vehicles with the idling stop systems operating frequently could cause more fuel consumption than vehicles without the idling stop systems. This study used the on-board automatic diagnosis system to connect to the Bluetooth OBDII(On Board Diagnostics) vehicle diagnostic device. The same vehicle and driving route were used to conduct this research. Two-stage tests were taken under simple road conditions and actual road conditions to analyze the experimental data, such as vehicle speed and fuel consumption. The experimental results showed that in the simple road condition case with IS (idling stop), 20.5% of fuel consumption was saved over the IC (idling continue). Under actual road conditions using the IS during weekday hours, more than 15% fuel consumption was saved. During peak traffic hours, IS only saved 3.67% of fuel consumption under the same conditions. However, if the idling stop time is less than 10 seconds, the fuel consumption increases.

Keywords: Idling stop systems, engine fuel consumption, traffic congested road conditions, OBDII, idling continue.

Suggested Citation: W.-K. Tseng, T.-J. Mai, " The Study of Fuel Consumption for Idling Stop Systems in Different Traffic Conditions," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 3(2), pp. 144-154, Mar-Apr 2025. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2025.3(2).13

INTRODUCTION

The idling stop system function allows stopping the engine when the vehicle needs to stop due to road conditions or traffic signs. At this time the driver depresses the brake and slows down. When the vehicle breaking speed is zero or close to zero the idling stop system automatically turns off the engine. At this time, the engine stops running so there is no fuel consumption or exhaust gas. When the road condition is removed and the vehicle can continue driving the driver releases the brake pedal and depresses the accelerator to start the engine. The engine automatically turns on to drive the vehicle. The idling stop system is usually controlled by the idling stop control unit to activate the

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

starter motor to achieve automatic start and stop operations during driving. In addition, there is usually an idling stop switch on the dashboard, which can be switched the disable or start the idling stop function, according to driving needs. Sarapon et al. [1] applied a vehicle without an idling stop system to cut off the fuel usage during engine idling to evaluate the data collected from the OBD data logger. This study included four levels of congestion and three roadside conditions. The spark ignition engine idling fuel consumption rate can be reduced by 40% under severe conditions. Diesel engine idling fuel consumption can be reduced by 30%.

Moritaka et al. [2] used two "Idle Stop" (IS) and "Idle Continuous" (IC) methods to study ways to improve fuel consumption. They used two vehicles of the same model, manufactured in the same year. Fuel flow meters with a degree of 1cc were installed on the two experimental vehicles, and the fuel consumption measured under 4 road conditions during idling (IS and IC). Their research results showed that the fuel consumption of IS vehicles was reduced by 4.0~8.7% over that of IC vehicles. In addition, the fuel consumed when the engine restarts is 1.20cc/time. If the idling stall ON-OFF frequency is too much, it will cause an invalid "Idle Stop" (IS) and the fuel consumption will be improved less. Abas et al. [3] used one-dimensional aerodynamics software to model a 1.6-liter PFI 4-cylinder engine to predict fuel consumption. The transient driving curve obtained from the actual road test on the Kuala Lumpur route was simulated. The fuel consumption was compared with the New European Drive Cycle (NEDC). The results provided useful insights and enabled manufacturers to evaluate and consider which of these two technologies (idling stop and cylinder deactivation) has a greater impact on fuel economy using the challenges of urban driving under Southeast Asian conditions.

Alessandrini et al. [4] defined the usage cycle concept to examine the factors affecting fuel consumption or emission pollution one by one. OBD II was used to read driving information and capture real-time vehicle driving using various parameter information. Comparing the Chassis Dynamometer test results, the difference in the data results was less than 3%, which proves that OBD II can be applied to fuel consumption research. Yang Diange et al. [5] used the real-time fuel consumption calculation method using the vehicle on-line fault diagnosis (OBD) system to collect and analyze the OBD real-time information on different types of vehicles. They carried out the actual vehicle experiment to verify the fuel consumption measurement method for gasoline vehicles. The results showed that this type of fuel consumption monitoring method can perform real-time online fuel consumption monitoring for most gasoline vehicles. The transient fuel consumption error was within $\pm 8\%$, and the total error was within $\pm 3\%$. Shen Jingxin [6] used the post office shortcut service vehicle to collect data. Using OBD II and the driving data was used to construct a speed-based fuel consumption model. An array of scenarios was assumed, with the practicality and applicability of the model discussed. Freight operators and drivers were provided with the ability to adjust driving behaviors through fuel consumption patterns according to different driving environments and route planning to reduce fuel consumption and achieve the purpose of energy saving and carbon reduction.

From another point of view, the Idling stop system can save fuel and exhaust gas production. However, in urban areas or rural road conditions, the frequent ON-OFF actions of the idling stop system may cause additional fuel consumption compared to repeated engine starts and battery power consumption. Under heavy traffic conditions, the idling stop system could consume more fuel than the system inactivated vehicle. This research used the On Board Diagnostics (OBD II) to connect the Bluetooth OBD measurement device to plan the vehicle under 1 simple road condition and 5 actual road conditions to measure the vehicle fuel consumption data with IS (idling stop) and IC (idling continue). The data were analyzed and compared for evaluating the energy-saving benefits of the idling stop system on Taiwan road conditions.

METHODS

The traditional idling stop system relies on the starter motor to restart the engine. Mazda's i-stop restarts the engine through combustion [7]. When the engine ignites to generate downward piston force, it injects fuel directly into the cylinder. As a result, the engine restarts quickly and quietly and

greatly saves fuel compared with other systems. In order to restart the engine using combustion, every time the engine is stopped, the piston stop position needs to be controlled during the gradual engine stop. The throttle valve actuation and the alternator control the piston at the compression top dead center position. The idling stop system actuation is shown in Figure 1.

MAZDA i-stop for Gasoline

Figure 1. MAZDA Idling Stop System Operation Situation

Source: [7]

HONDA has incorporated many innovative concepts into the engine design, including engine decompression technology, reverse rotation technology and silent start [8]. Usually when starting the engine it is necessary to compress the fuel and air mixture in the cylinder. This requires considerable power. As compensation, the exhaust valve in the PCX engine opens slightly when starting, reducing the power required for compression (the pressure reducing mechanism only runs at startup, not during normal engine operation). The reverse rotation technology is that before starting, the engine will slightly rotate in the opposite direction, so that the piston can "run start" in advance, making it easier to start the engine with less power. The ACG starter starts silently by integrating the starter motor and the magneto (generator). There is no gear meshing process in this way, so there is no motor gear meshing sound during cold start with automatic idling stop/start and hot stop/start. To achieve the muting effect, its ACG starter system structure is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. HONDA ACG STARTER System Structure

Source: [8]

The idling stop system launched by the French PSA Group equips with vehicles produced by Peugeot and Citroën [9]. To optimize fuel saving and make driving in STOP-START mode more stable, I-StARS can cut off the engine even before the vehicle comes to a complete stop. That is, as soon as the vehicle's speed falls below 8 km/h with an automated transmission and 20 km/h with a manual transmission, the i-StARS system will shut down the engine. The French PSA Group's idling stop system structure is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. PSA Peugeot Citroen Idling Stop System (i-StARS) Structure
Source: [9]

The Volkswagen Group idling stop system was jointly developed with Bosch [10]. It adopts a separate design. The starter and generator of this system are independent. The system parts are the same size as traditional parts, so it is easy to equip various vehicles with this technology. The system includes an engine control unit with software option start/stop, DC-DC converter 12V, electronic battery sensor, Start/Stop starter, neutral gear sensor, wheel speed sensor, crankshaft sensor, efficiency line generator etc.. Bosch continues to develop technology in cooperation with automakers that can be applied to autonomous vehicles and tested on the Volkswagen Passat, Porsche Panameras, Audi A8 and Fiat 500 minicar. The structure of the Volkswagen's idling stop system is shown in Figure 4.

There are currently three types of batteries used in fuel vehicles, namely SLI (starter battery), EFB (Enhanced Flooded Battery) and AGM (Absorbent Glass Mat) [11]. SLI is based on the battery named for the vehicle purpose, that is, Starting, Lighting, Ignition, which are used in traditional vehicles with no idling stop device. The EFB battery is an enhanced version of the SLI battery. It has a long service life, low internal resistance, approximately twice the number of charging cycles, and can carry a higher current. It is used for vehicles with idling stop devices and frequent charging and discharging requirements. However, it does not have a vehicle brake energy recovery system.

The AGM battery has the same advantages as the FEB battery. The number of charging cycles is about three times that of the traditional battery. It can also be used in vehicles with idling stop devices and frequent charging and discharging requirements. AGM batteries are charged by the generator, but can also be recovered from braking kinetic energy. The system can be charged in a part of the charging range, so it can provide enough "extra" capacity to store the electric energy generated during braking. The three battery uses and the charging and discharging state during driving as shown in Figure 5. In addition, the special battery for the idling stop system and the traditional battery are based on the number of starts, cycle requirements, power supply of auxiliary equipment, battery capacity control during driving, and recharging status. The difference is shown in Table 1.

Figure 4. Bosch (Volkswagen) Idling Stop System Structure
Source: [10]

Figure 5. The Difference between SLI, FEB, and AGM Batteries
Source: [11]

Table 1. Comparison Table of the Differences between the Idling Stop Device Battery and the Traditional Battery

Traditional battery system	Special battery for idling stop device
Start the vehicle about 2~3 times a day	The vehicle needs to be started about 1~2km
Average number of starts 730 times/year	Average number of starts 17,500 times/year
Minimize cycle requirements	Battery continuous cycle demand
The auxiliary equipment needs the battery to be in the charging state	Attached equipment is powered when the engine turns off
The battery needs to be kept close to full charge	The battery is operating in a partially charged state
The battery is gradually recharged during the trip	The battery is quickly recharged during repeated engine shutdown modes

Source: [10]

The fuel consumption change curve is shown in Figure 6 [2], during the T1 period the engine keeps running at idle speed. At this time the idle speed, fuel consumption I is maintained. When the idling stop device is activated, the engine stops and the fuel consumption are instantaneously 0 and maintains Tis for this time. When the engine restarts additional fuel consumption (S2) and fuel consumption caused by battery recharging (S3) will occur. The additional fuel consumption will return to the original idling fuel consumption I after the TR time has elapsed. Therefore, the fuel consumption of S2 and S3 generated during the TR time is the additional fuel consumption when the idling stop device is activated. In actual road conditions due to serious traffic jams or the interval between traffic lights is too short, the engine stops period decreases and the engine restarting frequency increases. The additional fuel consumption S2 and S3 increase at this time. It is possible that when the idling stop system is activated, it will consume more fuel than when the engine is not stopped.

Figure 6. Fuel Consumption Change Curve

Source: [2]

The equation for estimating the fuel consumption amount F_s can be expressed by the following equation [2].

$$F_s = I \times (T_{is}) - (S_2 + S_3) \quad (1)$$

Where

Fs : Saved fuel consumption (cc)

I : Fuel consumption during idling (cc/s)

Tis : Period during the idling stop (s)

S 2 : Additional fuel consumption by restarting the engine (cc)

S3 : Energy consumption at the battery for starting, in fuel consumption equivalence (cc)

According to the experimental data proposed by Moritaka et al. [2], assuming that the engine is restarted after the idling stop period is only 7 seconds, the formula $F_s = 0.171 \cdot 7 - 1.20$ and the fuel consumption $F_s = -0.003$ (cc) the calculation results show that if the engine is stopped for less than 7 seconds the idling stop device may consume more fuel than the traditional engine without idling stop.

PROCEDURE AND RESULTS

This research used the On Board Diagnostics (OBD II) to connect to the Bluetooth OBD measurement device to measure the vehicle test data under simple and actual road conditions. The fuel consumption data for the vehicles with IS or IC are recorded during driving for analysis. In the initial experiment stage the experimental equipment is connected and the experiment data interception test is planned. If the data interception is normal, road condition tests will be carried out. The flowchart of the experiment is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. The Flowchart of the Experiment

The test vehicles were the 2011 Mazda 5 1997cc and the 2021 VW T6.1 Caravelle 150L 1968cc two models. The Mazda 5 model was used for simple road condition test. The main function was to confirm the initial experiment stage. The experimental equipment and data measurement operations were carried out to confirm the basic experiment with the car model without idling stop system. After the simple road condition test was finished the car model VW T6.1 was used to perform the actual road condition fuel consumption test of the idling stop system. The experimental vehicles are shown in Figures 8 and 9. The vehicle specifications are shown in Tables 4 and 5.

Figure 8. Photo of the Mazda 5 Test Vehicle

Figure 9. Photo of the VW T6.1 Caravelle Test Vehicle

The first test stage was carried out on a vehicle without idling stop device under simple road conditions. The safety of the test was considered. Open spaces were used to simulate an idling stop and wait tests under heavy traffic. The test was designed to drive in a complete square on a road with 4 right hand turn stops. Traffic signs were simulated with 4 waiting points. The stopping time was set at 10 seconds. The IS and IC fuel consumptions were compared with the same driving route, vehicle, and without air conditioning. The IS and IC fuel consumptions were obtained by intercepting OBD data. The test route of the fuel consumption for simple road conditions is shown in Figure 10.

The test results showed that under the IC condition waiting for 10 seconds, the average idling fuel consumption rate was 0.2490cc/s, the average idling fuel consumption for the trip was 13.45cc, and the total fuel consumption for the trip is 53.48cc. Compared to the IS condition for 10 seconds the average idling fuel consumption rate is 0cc/s, the average idling fuel consumption of the trip is 0cc, and the total fuel consumption of the trip is 42.52cc. Under simple road conditions, the IS can save 20.5% of fuel consumption.

Figure 10. Test Route of the Fuel Consumption for Simple Road Conditions

The second test phase was carried out with vehicles equipped with an idling stop system under actual road conditions. The objective was to measure the idling stop and waiting conditions on 5 road sections in Taichung during peak traffic and weekday traffic. The IS and IC fuel consumptions were obtained with the same driving route, vehicle and with air conditioning off. By acquiring OBD data to analyze the IS and IC fuel consumptions, the test route of the fuel consumption for actual road conditions is shown in Figure 11. The whole trip took about 22.2km. The test was conducted in two periods, including 08:30 ~09:30 traffic peak time and 10:30~11:30 weekday traffic hours. The IS and IC fuel consumptions were tested during the same time periods.

Figure 11. Test Route of the Fuel Consumption for Actual Road Conditions

The test results from 22.2km actual road conditions include 4 tests, peak time IS, peak time IC, weekday IS and weekday IC. The test results are shown in Table 2. The fuel consumption with IS conditions during the peak time traffic saved only 98.14cc of the fuel compared to the fuel consumption with IC conditions and the fuel economy was about 3.67%. The fuel consumption with

IS and IC conditions during the weekday were compared, the IS conditions saved 329cc of fuel, with about 15% fuel economy.

Table 2. Fuel Consumption Test Results for Actual Road Conditions

Driving condition				
peak time /weekday hour	peak time	peak time	weekday hour	weekday hour
Idling stop	on	off	on	off
Total driving time (s)	3821	4547	3038	3535
Total mileage (km)	22.2	22.2	22.2	22.2
Proportion of waiting state in total time (%)	38.9%	38.7%	27.6%	32.2%
Idle fuel consumption (cc)	374.76	585.89	33.1	362.1
Total fuel consumption (cc)	2564.99	2663.13	1819.73	2164.90
Fuel economy (%)	3.67		15.94	

The 22.2km test route was subdivided into 5 road types, including residential areas, urban areas, highways, express roads and suburbs. The fuel economy of the idling stop system was compared using various road types during peak time and weekdays. The test results are shown in Table 3 and Table 4. Among them, highways and expressways under normal traffic conditions, vehicles usually would not be stopped, but there were certain stopping conditions for connecting road after leaving the interchange depending on the traffic flow condition. According to the test results, during peak time and weekdays. the vehicle with the idling stop system has better fuel economy saving about 38.50%~39.95%.

Table 3. Actual Road Conditions Test Results from Various Road Types during Peak Time

result road	1		2		3		4		5	
	IS	IC	IS	IC	IS	IC	IS	IC	IS	IC
km	4.1km		4.0		5.0km		4.9km		4.2km	
Road type	Residential area		Urban area		highway		Expressway		suburb	
Stop frequency (times/km)	1.71	1.71	2.00	3.75	1.60	2.20	0.20	0.41	2.38	0.71
Average speed (km/h)	16.52	11.48	13.04	8.68	25.48	22.14	39.90	36.32	16.26	26.56
Average waiting time (s)	45.57	53.57	70.88	56.67	34.37	37.27	31	31.5	29	23.67
Invalid waiting time (s)	7	-	0	-	5	-	0	-	7	-
Idle fuel consumption (cc)	59.85	136.19	82.69	275.43	169.95	130.93	16.65	19.94	45.62	23.40
Total fuel consumption (cc)	393.39	451.37	457.48	761.83	839.15	674.71	510.26	430.73	364.72	344.6
Fuel economy (%)	12.85		39.95		-19.60		-12.99		-5.52	

Table 4. Actual Road Conditions Test Results from Various Road Types during Weekdays

result road	1		2		3		4		5	
	IS	IC	IS	IC	IS	IC	IS	IC	IS	IC
km	4.1km		4.0		5.0km		4.9km		4.2km	
Road type	Residential area		Urban area		highway		Expressway		suburb	
Stop frequency (times/km)	1.21	0.96	2.00	2.75	1.4	0.2	0.41	0.41	0	0.95
Average speed (km/h)	19.28	19.72	14.65	10.73	33.09	40.63	40.45	38.59	39.61	22.22
Average waiting time (s)	45.2	43.75	48.7	63.55	17.14	18	22.5	30.5	0	37
Invalid waiting time (s)	0	-	3	-	10	-	5	-	0	-

Idle fuel consumption (cc)	14.19	55.58	3.83	221.89	7.75	5.94	6.38	19.38	0	59.32
Total fuel consumption (cc)	334.77	362.63	378.63	615.70	437.87	414.42	390.81	413.20	277.23	358.96
Fuel economy (%)	7.68		38.50		-5.36		5.42		22.77	

CONCLUSIONS

In this study vehicles with idling stop system were used to conduct the fuel consumption test. During the tests, the idling stop time and average idling fuel consumption rate were measured using the same vehicle, path and driving conditions. The idling fuel consumption rate with idling stop on/off was compared with a simple road condition with a stop time of 10 seconds. In the IC state the average idling fuel consumption rate was 0.2490cc/s. The total fuel consumption was 53.48cc. In the IS state the engine was manually turned off when the vehicle was stopped, so the idling fuel consumption was 0cc/s, and the total fuel consumption was 42.52cc. In the simple road condition case, the IS state had a fuel economy of about 20.5% compared to the IC state. In the actual road condition test under normal driving conditions, vehicles with IS state had about 15% better fuel economy than those with the IC state on weekdays. In addition, during peak traffic the fuel consumption for vehicles with IS state is lower than that for vehicles with the IC state. The fuel only saved 211.13cc (about 3.67%). The fuel consumption on various road types was analyzed. It was found that after driving on highway, in order to cool the engine or turbo, even when the driver's idling stop system switch was on, the vehicle did not automatically turn off the engine at idling. This resulted in poor fuel efficiency. In the overall driving situation, starting the idling stop system during driving has a certain fuel saving effect.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Thitipatanapong, N. Noomwongs, R. Thitipatanapong, and S. Chantranuwathana, "A comparison study on saving fuel by idle-stop system in Bangkok traffic condition," SAE Technical Paper 2013-01-0069, 2013, doi: 10.4271/2013-01-0069.
- [2] M. Matsuura, K. Korematsu, and J. Tanaka, "Fuel consumption improvement of vehicles by idling stop," SAE Technical Paper 2004-01-1896, 2004, doi: 10.4271/2004-01-1896.
- [3] M. Abas, S. Zainal Abidin, S. Rajoo, R. Martinez-Botas, and M. Ismail, "Evaluation between engine stop/start and cylinder deactivation technologies under Southeast Asia urban driving condition," SAE Technical Paper 2017-01-0986, 2017.
- [4] A. Alessandrini, F. Filippi, F. Orecchini, and F. Ortenzi, "A new method for collecting vehicle behavior in daily use for energy and environmental analysis," Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng., Part D, vol. 220, no. 11, pp. 1527–1537, Aug. 2006.
- [5] J. Yang and M. Lee, "Fuel consumption detection of vehicle based on," Vehicle Safety Magazine, vol. 7, 2016.
- [6] J. Shen, "Fuel consumption analysis of urban driving," M.S. thesis, National Chiao Tung University, 2013.
- [7] Mazda i-stop. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mazda.com/en/innovation/technology/env/i-stop/>
- [8] Honda ACG. [Online]. Available: <https://forum.jorsindo.com/thread-2486620-1-2.html>
- [9] PSA i-StARS. [Online]. Available: <https://www.autoevolution.com/news/psa-peugeot-citroen-to-introduce-new-stopstart-system-21282.html>
- [10] Bosch Stop-Start System. [Online]. Available: https://www.greencarreports.com/news/1047743_bosch-develops-engine-stop-start-system-for-automatics
- [11] Automotive Batteries. [Online]. Available: <https://www.varta-automotive.com/en-gb/zh-tw>

